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Requirements for future economics in the transition to the digital economy

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Annotation: In this article, in the process of transition to the digital economy, the demands placed on the teachers of "Information and communication technologies and systems in the economy" and students studying in the field of economics, as well as the solutions aimed at solving them, are interpreted.

Key words: globalization, digitization of society, digital technologies, smart city, smart house, information technologies in the economy, presentation, advertising.

1 Introduction

The use of information technologies and communication tools in all spheres of society has become the main priority of the development of this sphere. In particular, the use of information technologies in the field of economy, which is the body and foundation of the society, has taken the main place in the development of the sector.

The word "digitalization" is actually a new term, which refers to the involvement of IT solutions in the process of innovative management and administration, and as a result, the use of information technologies in all systems, from Internet of Things to e-government.

As the importance and impact of digitalization increases, it can be seen that the requirements for future economics students will also change. The reason is that the digitization process is directly implemented by economists and representatives of the IT sector.

2020 was announced as the "Year of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy Development" in our country, and the work in this regard has now reached a new level, and the country's "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy and the "Road Map" for its implementation were approved by presidential decree.

It can be seen from the instructions on the development of digital education within the framework of this strategy that the digitization process is directly entering the education system.

Literature analysis

Starting from January 1, 2021, a system will be introduced to reimburse citizens up to 50% of the costs of obtaining international IT certificates in areas such as system administration, database and cloud platform management, information security, and other areas of high demand;

By January 1, 2021, digital technology training centers will be opened in each district and city based on existing infrastructure facilities for the general population, especially youth and women;

By the end of 2023, more than 200 specialized schools for in-depth teaching of computer science and information technologies will be gradually established in all districts and cities on the basis of existing educational institutions to promote the creative development of students and learn the basics of computer programming.

As it may seem at first glance, blended learning is not a new approach to effective learning. This format has actually been around for over two decades, and many universities are now using this form of education. It is thanks to this method that a student has the opportunity to study individually, in a group, and additionally at home at a time convenient for him.

3 Results and discussions

The sector that starts working with a specialist who does not have the knowledge and skills related to the digitization process will lag behind the development of society.

A specialist who has not mastered the knowledge and skills associated with the digitization process will have problems finding his place in society.

The labor market cannot cope with competition. As a result, the probability of unemployment increases.

In the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, special attention is paid to the introduction of digital technologies and modern methods in the educational process. increased:

1. Organization of a system of training highly qualified specialist-technical personnel for the digital economy;
2. Ensuring the solid integration of modern information and communication technologies and educational technologies, creating additional conditions for the continuous development of the professional skills of pedagogues in this regard; To ensure the implementation of the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated 23.09.2019 No. 797 on additional measures to further improve the system of improving the qualifications of managers and pedagogues of higher education institutions.
3. In the educational process, individualization based on digital technologies, development of distance education services, wide introduction of webinar, online, "Blended learning", "flepped classroom" technologies into practice;

In this, traditional education and distance education are combined. Depending on the needs and capabilities of the students, they can use the types of education.

In the "Flapped classroom" technology, the teacher places all the information on the platform. Students are preparing at home with information about the lessons. There are no lectures during the lesson, students learn at home and strengthen their practical skills with the help of practical exercises.

4. Organization of distance education programs based on modern information and communication technologies (8): It is advisable to use the services of Zoom, Microsoft Teams, FreeConference video conference programs.

The process of transition to the digital economy puts the following issues before educational institutions that prepare experts in the field of economics:

- Providing the educational process with complete information technologies. Creation of special laboratory rooms and simulators for practice and laboratory training.
- Involve qualified professors and teachers who are real masters of their work in the educational process. Attracting a narrow range of specialists working with special programs
- Use of modern educational methods and information technologies. In this case, based on the given topic, a different approach to each topic and the use of methods
- Creation and implementation of the opportunity to master the special software used in the fields.

✓ **MICROSOFT EXCEL**- A universal program included in the Microsoft Office suite of programs. An unrivalled program for working with spreadsheets with the ability to store, organize and analyze information. Flexible and easy to use.

✓ **1C: ACCOUNTING** is the most popular accounting program that has taken accounting to a whole new level. The services connected to it work effectively with accounting tasks. The main features of this program are:

accounting in accordance with the law, registration of business operations, timely support of users.

✓ **1C: SALARY AND HR MANAGEMENT** this program allows you to automate matters related to the calculation of wages and the implementation of the organization's personnel policy. Widely used in personnel department and accounting department.

✓ **1C: DOCUMENT EXCHANGE** a modern ECM system (Enterprise Content Management), a comprehensive set of tools for business process management and employee performance. It serves to automate work with documents in the organization. Significantly reduces the duration of management decisions.

✓ **SBIS SYSTEM** includes many possibilities, such as electronic document circulation within the organization and counterparties, reporting to all government bodies via the Internet, corporate social network (news and discussions, reposts, likes and comments), point of sale, etc.

✓ **GLONASS/GPS** - is a modern tool that allows you to monitor the real-time movement of the car, the mode of work and rest of the driver, the speed of the car and fuel consumption. An ideal solution for the economist who controls fuel lubricants.

✓ **CLIENT-BANK** is a convenient system, through which the client can perform settlement operations, exchange information and documents with the bank by phone and computer.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that it is necessary to connect the educational process directly with economic spheres, to involve economic experts in the educational process, to familiarize with the legal documents and decisions related to the sphere. It is the responsibility of the educational institution to ensure the direct participation of students in the digitization process, to improve their practical skills by involving them in the processes, to create conditions for digitization and mastering the software used in the economic spheres.

These processes directly require the teaching staff teaching "Information Communication Technologies and Systems in the Economy" to be constantly aware of the innovations and inventions related to IT and Economy. 1C accounting, 1C: document exchange, 1C: payroll and personnel management, SBIS SYSTEM, GLONASS/GPS, CLIENT-BANK, PlanFakt, Microsofr Power, used in economic fields in addition to the topics included in the lesson plan from students studying economics Independent study of BI, Qlik Sense, Seneco, Luxms BI, Modus BI, Insight, Business Scanner, Dashboard24, Visiology(10) and other programs is a guarantee of becoming a mature specialist.

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10. <https://www.clouderp.ru/tools/bi/> udied in the system of language units and should not be placed above them as a supra-linguistic phenomenon.